

List of Survey Questions Conducted at ZY Education Technology Co. Ltd.

Basic information of the participated teenage students (Demographics and Locations):

Gender: male/female

Country: China/U.S

Grade: 7-12

Survey Questions:

Question 1: "Do you prefer online or offline education?"

Question 2: "How familiar are you with research education for teenagers on a scale of 1-10?"

Question 3: "How interested are you in research education on a scale of 1-10?"

Question 4: "Have you been exposed to research education during your school studies?
(Yes/No)"

Question 5: "How much has the COVID pandemic impacted your studies and daily life on a scale of 1-10?"

Question 6: "How much has the COVID pandemic affected your studies and daily life on a scale of 1-10?"

Question 7: "To what extent has the pandemic made you lean towards online education on a scale of 1-10?"

Question 8: "Which type of educational platform do you prefer for research education? (e.g., online platforms, offline courses, blended learning, etc.)"

Question 9: "Do you believe that research education is beneficial for the future career development of teenagers? (on a scale of 1-10)"